

Formation of a self-organisational culture of students studying in pedagogical universities

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ABSTRACT: University education aims annually to improve the quality of knowledge transferred to students in order to further accelerate and renew human capital. However, to obtain professional knowledge and practical skills students need to organise their independent work productively, clearly managing a limited amount of time and taking more responsibility for the final result. For this reason, it is important to determine the relationship between different forms of learning activities, the student's personal qualities, the level of motivation for learning and the skills of self-regulation that can ensure the successful achievement of learning outcomes. Accordingly, within the scope of this study, it is aimed to inquire about the current level of formation of a self-organisational culture, the difficulties encountered in organising students' independent work, and their opinions and their satisfaction with the existing forms of independent work at the university. The study sample included 150 individuals studying at Abai University (Kazakhstan). Data were analysed using t-test (two-sample). An attempt is made to develop a model for the formation of a self-organisational culture of students and guidance is provided to pedagogical university teachers to foster the development of a resilient self-organisational culture.

Keywords: Educational And Professional Activities, Higher Education, Model Of A Self-Organisational Culture, Self-Organisational Culture.

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1. Introduction

The system of modern education is aimed at creating conditions optimal for the self-realisation of the person, the desire for personal and professional development. Modern university education is aimed at creating favourable conditions for disclosing students' unique talents, interests, and intellectual potential.

The process of professional training and the formation of competitive modern students is possible in the conditions of self-management of educational activities. Ensuring the development of the student's individuality and fulfilment of his tasks of educational and professional activity becomes possible through the development of self-regulatory skills. Self-regulation refers to an individual's ability to manage their thoughts, emotions, and behaviours in order to achieve a desired outcome. It involves setting goals, creating plans, and monitoring progress, as well as the ability to regulate one's emotions and behaviours in response to changing circumstances (Loksha, 2002).

The development of self-regulation is important for several reasons. Firstly, it allows individuals to take control of their own lives and make decisions that align with their goals and values. This is particularly important for students and professionals, who need to be able to manage their time and tasks effectively in order to be successful.

Secondly, the development of self-regulation promotes the development of integral individuality. This refers to the idea that each person is a unique individual with their own strengths, weaknesses, and potential for growth. By developing self-regulation skills, individuals are better able to understand themselves and their own abilities, and to make choices that align with their own goals and values.

Finally, the development of self-regulation is important for success in educational and professional activities. Students and professionals who are able to manage their time, emotions, and behaviours effectively are more likely to be successful in their chosen fields, as they are able to set and achieve goals, work collaboratively with others, and adapt to changing circumstances.

The concept of competitiveness is studied by various scientists who see different sources as the basis for it. A. Maslow highlights self-actualization as the key to competitiveness. He defines self-actualization as the full utilisation of an individual's talents, abilities, and opportunities. According to Maslow, an individual's ability to be competitive is dependent on their ability to fully realise their potential (Maslow, 1999).

R. Martens believes that the fundamental basis to success and competitiveness is an individual's social competence. Social competence refers to an individual's ability to effectively utilise their personal qualities, knowledge, skills, and abilities in various social roles. An individual's social competence is a critical factor in their ability to compete and be successful (Martens, 1979).

A. Bandura also sees the acquisition of knowledge and the ability to adapt behaviour to fit specific situations as a critical source of competitiveness. Individuals who are able to actively acquire knowledge and use it to adapt their behaviour to changing circumstances are better equipped to compete and succeed (Bandura, 2000).

Overall, these different perspectives on the sources of competitiveness highlight the importance of various factors, such as self-actualization, social competence, and the ability to acquire and utilise knowledge. By understanding these different sources of competitiveness, individuals can work to develop the skills and abilities necessary to compete and succeed in various aspects of their lives.

The cultivation of a self-organisational culture plays a crucial role in students' acquisition of knowledge, skills, and abilities throughout their educational and professional journey. This culture is nurtured through the attentive guidance of subject teachers and supervisors on a daily basis. However, as students progress towards their chosen professions, the responsibility for independent learning, time management, and monitoring educational progress shifts entirely to the students themselves.

In order to become a successful and highly skilled professional, it is essential for individuals to possess the ability to autonomously chart the course of their future career development. To facilitate this, it becomes vital to enhance the self-organisational culture among students. This culture serves as a foundational element for them to cultivate the modern and competitive skill set required in their respective fields (Kotova, 2012).

Since the onset of 2020, the ability of students to independently organise their educational and cognitive activities has faced rigorous testing due to the widespread adoption of online and distance learning (Gorban, Guba, Mosol, Hrandt, and Lukasevich, 2022). The rapid evolution of learning conditions and formats has brought forth unforeseen challenges for students in pedagogical universities, problematic situations that were not as apparent in traditional classroom settings. As a result, there has been a heightened emphasis on the selection of effective teaching methods and increased examination of students' knowledge by university lecturers.

2. Literature Review

The concept of self-organisation began to be studied by researchers in the middle of the 20th century, acting as the basis for controlling arbitrary processes of a system. W. Ross Ashby first defined and introduced the term "self-organising system" into the scientific language in 1947. Self-organisation occurs when a system composed of many interacting elements spontaneously forms patterns or structures without external guidance or control. This phenomenon is often associated with the emergence of complexity, where the collective behaviour of a system's components gives rise to new properties that cannot be attributed to any individual part of the system (Ashby, 1947).

Within the framework of cybernetics, the concept of self-organisation was first studied by foreign scientists (Wiener, 1961; Ashby, 1966, etc.), and then by representatives of the scientific community of the Soviet Union (Lerner, 1967; Yudin, 1970; Pushkin, 1974, etc.).

According to the author of the cybernetic approach, N. Wiener, the exchange of information in living beings and machines has similarities, which based on the features of self-organisation can further contribute to the formation of cybernetic systems and artificial intelligence (Wiener N., 1958). Being a complex dynamic system, self-organisation in

cybernetics is capable, taking into account previous experience, of maintaining or improving its organisation under the influence of external and internal changes (Pushkin V.G., 1974). Complexity, adaptability, striving for balance, reliability, flexibility and sustainability were highlighted as the main characteristics of self-organising systems.

Collecting new knowledge, the concept of «self-organisation» gradually passes from cybernetics to philosophy and is perceived as the highest form of development of dynamic systems, which acts as a general scientific concretization of the philosophical principle of self-development (Astafyev A.K., 1988; Vedmedev M.M., 1988; Gorelov A.A., 1990, etc.). Based on a synergistic approach, man is viewed as a complex, open and self-developing system (N.N. Moiseyev, T. Niit, G. Allport, M. Chernushek), which at the present stage of development is able to interact with the surrounding world and reality (I. Prigozhin, G. Haken, V.P. Treasurer, N.N. Moiseyev). If a complex organised system is open, it has the characteristics of self-organisation, which allows it to regulate the future state and development of the system, accelerating its evolution.

Based on the thoughts of the German theoretical physicist H.Haken, systems can be defined as self-organising, provided that they can acquire any spatial, temporal or functional structure without being subjected to external specific influence (Haken, 2006). In this sense, if we conceive of man as a unified biological system without external influence, which can independently organise and control internal processes, then this confirms the above-mentioned scientists' thoughts that man is capable of independently organising his activities consciously, giving them an arbitrary character.

As a biological system that follows its laws of development, each individual student represents a self-organising system capable of adapting to certain internal and external conditions. According to Zimnyaya, independent work is defined as objective and internally motivated and encompasses the deliberate actions of a subject performed in a structured manner, and self-correction is an important aspect of both the process and the result. Successful engagement in independent work requires a considerable degree of self-conscience, reflective capabilities, self-discipline and personal responsibility. These characteristics contribute to the effective execution of independent tasks and tasks as individuals independently navigate their learning journey, take ownership of their academic pursuits and monitor and adapt their progress towards the objectives they desire (Zimnyaya, 1991).

An ability to adapt to changing circumstances and overcome complex challenges is crucial to professional success. The self-organisational culture equips students with the flexibility and resilience they need to thrive in a varied and dynamic environment. Beyond academic endeavours, self-organisation skills can be applied to various areas of life, and students can balance academic pursuits, personal commitments and extracurricular activities.

In the educational process of modern universities, the role of students has changed considerably. They move from passive subjects to active participants in their educational and professional activities. Therefore, the educational approach emphasises the activation of self-directed and creative students in their studies and future careers. However, the achievement of this change requires traditional scientific and methodological support for

specialist training. As a result, the demand for more active and dynamic forms of teaching, learning and evaluation is increasing. In order to effectively implement these methods, it is essential that students develop the abilities for self-organising their educational and professional activities. Basically, modern universities strive to give students autonomy by transforming their role from passive recipients to active participants in the education process. This requires a shift to a more engaged and active teaching methodology in which students take over the learning journey. In order to excel in such an environment, students must develop self-organisation skills and manage their academic and professional careers effectively (Kotova, 2012).

According to our domestic scientists who study problems of Kazakhstani higher education and a process of its organisation, it is important to mention Stukalenko, Naviy, and Menlibekova's views that pointed to the main outcomes of the education process studied include the cognitive activity of prospective teachers, their professional competences and their recognition of the importance of cognitive participation and personal self-education. In addition, this process is characterised by a remarkable level of motivation and self-management. Effective communication focuses on business-related issues and promotes the development of cognitive abilities, creative thinking and strong interpersonal skills (Stukalenko, Naviy, Menlibekova, 2016).

The research conducted by Yertargynkyzy, Akhmetova, Arinova, and Moldassan confirmed that motivations for professional education and education are interconnected with self-development in professional education and education activities. The results showed a significant positive correlation between the level of professional and educational motivation and the ability to undertake self-development. Higher levels of motivation are associated with greater capacity for professional and pedagogical self-improvement and ultimately contribute to the formation of professional ideals among students (Yertargynkyzy, Akhmetova, Arinova, Moldassan, 2016).

An essential aspect of teacher-educators' training is to emphasise the importance of self-awareness, self-reflection, and self-regulation for professional development. This involves the promotion of independent work and the transition to personalised training and education plans. These measures collectively contribute to improving the competence and effectiveness of teachers and educators in their role (Abibulaeva, 2002).

Domestic researchers are studying the components of self-organisation in students' educational activities, focusing on developing the skills of university teachers in effectively organising academic work and personal life. These components include:

- the ability to set targets and the motivation to achieve these targets;
- their dedication and creativity in their efforts;
- skillfully plan and organise their activities;
- engage in self-reflection and necessary self-correction (Agranovich, 2020).

By developing these components, students will have valuable tools to successfully navigate their educational journey and personal growth.

The development of self-organisation skills depends heavily on the nature of communication in the "teacher-student" dialogue. However, empirical evidence suggests

that traditional methods of interaction between teachers and students still dominate the education process. Students rarely engage in the formation of their educational path, and forms of interaction with teachers are usually frontal and without personalisation. As a result, the necessity to establish a personality-oriented interaction between university teachers and students is clearly contradictory to the actual experience of such interactions.

The educational research has illuminated the different requirements students encounter when entering universities. These conditions include various aspects of educational activities, the interaction dynamics within student groups and relations with teachers. The transition from school to university requires a re-evaluation of the traditional teacher-student relationship, and certain "school" dynamics may not be suitable and effective in the university environment. This imbalance may hinder the development of healthy relationships between students and teachers and may even alter the overall structure of educational communication.

3. Methodology

Research Design

This paper uses the following research methods:

1. At the theoretical level, the analysis of pedagogical and social literature was used to clarify the concept and create a model of "self-organisation culture";

2. At the empirical level, students were asked to identify the current level of self-organisation abilities based on six basic criteria: planning, purposefulness, persistence, persistence, self-organisation and current orientation.

3. Statistical analysis method - T-Test: Two samples with equal variances were used for statistical data analysis and hypotheses testing.

We designed the process of forming a culture of self-organization using a descriptive model. The use of a descriptive model allowed us to solve several problems:

- Study of an object (scientific research) – to most fully and accurately reflect the properties of the object;

- control – most accurately reflect the properties of an object in the operating range of changes in its parameters;

- forecasting – build a model that can most accurately predict the behavior of an object in the future;

- training – reflect the studied properties of the object in the model. The construction of a descriptive model occurs according to the following scheme: observation, coding, recording (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. sequence of constructing a descriptive model

The descriptive model of self-organizational culture formation of students focuses on the implementation of the strategy for the development of the educational process at university and includes a set of its components: target, theoretical and methodological, scientific and pedagogical, practice-oriented, technological, methodological, effective.

The basic principles of operation of such a model should be:

- purposefulness, consistency and consistency of the educational process, focused not so much on one-time actions (which under certain conditions cannot lose their significance), but on cyclical and long-term programs;
- reliance on positive models of student behavior and their formation directly in the student environment;
- setting up direct personal contact between students and teachers,
- close connection between extracurricular work and the educational process.

The study revealed that in order to substantiate the process of forming self-organizational culture among students, it is necessary to take into account internal and external factors.

We include the following as internal factors: awareness of the personal importance of a culture of self-organization; focus on mastering the values of general culture and the culture of self-organization; a person's understanding of a generalized rule and updating of knowledge.

To external factors: understanding the essence of the culture of self-organization as a certain set of personal qualities, actions and operations of its components and methods of performing actions; organization of practical activities, participation in projects and events to develop a culture of self-organization; reflection on the level of development of the culture of self-organization; accounting and evaluation of the progress and results of activities.

Figure 2 the model of self-organizational culture

Let us consider the substantive nature of the generic concept of our study

“self-organizational culture of students”, based on the criteria for determining the structure.

The main criterion for assessing the culture of self-organization of students is practical meaning. Zaenutdinova(2000) notes this criterion in her study and emphasizes that a practical manifestation of the self-organizational culture of students is human self-regulation, which includes a mechanism for managing one’s own physiological states (psychological states), behavior or actions. The next criterion is the form of presentation of the structure of students’ self-organization culture. Analysis of the structural components in models related to the culture of self-organization of students (V. Graf’s model of organizing life time , N.M. Peisakhov’s system of self-government) and the structure of educational self-organization by Ustinova (2000) made it possible to identify the most important components of this process:

goal setting, situation analysis, planning or control, correction. We consider it appropriate to point these components along with personal qualities, that is, with the qualities of the subject that allow him to initiate the mechanism of organizing himself and his activities.

According to the target criterion, the need for planning and achieving set goals is formed through the exerted volitional efforts. From the point of view of T.N. Noskova and A.S. Kulikova, the target component is also responsible for positive motivation for the formation of students' self-organization skills in the information environment. This aspect, as understood by the authors, is characterized by the acceptance and retention of goals, awareness of processes or actions. An individual with developed goal-setting independently puts forward goals, independently and consciously organizes his activities to achieve them, moreover, his goal is realistic (in detail) or sustainable. With the help of the reflexive criterion of the culture of self-organization of students, the need for forecasting, planning and analysis of the activities performed is formed on the basis of reflexive actions, management with a clearly expressed position

"itself". Self-government is an important element of management. A detailed analyzing component, which, in the interpretation of Surgutskova(2017) is associated with the ability to look into the future and determine the prospects for activity; it is aimed at assessing one's own activities and making the necessary adjustments. It also allows you to develop abilities for self-knowledge, work on yourself and use them in professional development.

As a rule, within the framework of the personal criterion, personal qualities are improved to develop the skills of target and reflexive groups. The analysis carried out revealed important theoretical principles concerning the content and structure of students' self-organization culture. They will be used later.

In our opinion, the culture of self-organization of a student's personality is a type of personal culture with a high level of organization of oneself and one's activities, which is formed in the process of self-development on the basis of the value attitude of future specialists to independence, on the basis of the desire for effectiveness in all types of activities, manifested in the formed skills and abilities planning, monitoring the results of one's actions, which provides the opportunity to recognize oneself as a subject of one's own life, capable of choosing rational and optimal ways to solve professional problems. Let us present the self-organizational culture of students in the form of a structural and content model in Figure 1

Its essence lies in the student's awareness of his own role in the success of educational, cognitive and further professional activities, in the student's desire for self-organization (streamlining the goals and motives of self-development, skills of self-control and self-regulation of mental states, abilities for self-analysis and adequate self-esteem), as well as these actions themselves on personal self-organization, fixed in the student's mind as habitual and necessary.

Such an understanding of self-organizational culture of higher education students allows us to identify its component composition.

We defined the structure of self-organizational culture of university students as a unity of interconnected and interdependent components: knowledge and needs, abilities, skills, competencies, personal qualities, values, abilities.

In a more detailed description, we are dealing with the knowledge component, namely, ideological and subject-specific knowledge about the culture of self-organization, with students' ideas about themselves as a subject of the culture of self-organization. The next activity component, containing skills and abilities, is responsible for mastering the skills of a culture of self-organization, mastering the ability to use the means of goal setting, planning, and organizing one's activities in one's activities. The formed competence component of the culture of self-organization orients students towards cooperation, towards a conscious desire for professional and personal growth, towards self-knowledge and self-improvement. A set of personal qualities represents a motivational component and reflects the motivation to form a culture of self-organization and allows one to strive for professional success. The value component is represented by the adoption of the values of a culture of self-organization, the integration of personal and professional values and meanings. The reflective component is responsible for reflective abilities, the ability to evaluate and analyze oneself and the results of one's activities.

Each component performs its own function: knowledge - cognitive, activity, competence - activity-operational, motivational - educational, value - value-oriented, reflexive - reflexive - developmental.

To understand the self-organizational culture of university students, it is necessary to clarify the concepts "educational activities" and "extracurricular activities", since it is in these types of activities that we consider the structural components of self-organizational culture and the functions associated with them. The concept of "activity" is often used as a synonym for the concepts of "teaching" and "educational work". "Activity" in Russian is called occupation, work. From the point of view of usage, the words "study work" and "educational activity" can indeed be used as synonyms. Although in our understanding, these concepts are not identical. Learning is a process that occurs during studying. According to Elkonin (1993) learning is the process of a person's assimilation of knowledge in various types of activities or forms of communication with other people. Babansky (2002) understands by educational activity not only the student's leading activity in acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities; as well as the work of a teacher in the form of helping the diverse education and development of students.

Extracurricular activities of students are activities that are not related to the educational process. It is aimed mainly at the development of creative abilities and self-realization of students, which do not correlate with their future profession or are indirectly related to it. It is important to note that the completely voluntary nature of extracurricular activities implies the desire of the student himself, and not the instructions of the management of the educational organization.

In the framework of our study, educational activities include scientific, educational and cognitive, academic, educational and professional and independent work. In extracurricular activities we distinguish the following types: communicative, spiritual and moral, social, artistic and creative, sports and recreational.

Sample and Data Collection

The Self-Organization Activities Questionnaire developed by M. Bond and N. Feather (1988) and translated and extended by E.Y. Mandrikova (2010) was the basis. The main objective of the questionnaire was to determine the extent to which tactical planning and strategic goal-setting skills developed, reflecting the level of self-organisation and self-regulatory activity as a whole.

The basis for the study became the leading national pedagogical university in Kazakhstan - Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University. Primary and secondary students from Abai University were selected to participate in the study. The total number of students was 150. The number of students by course is as follows:

- 1st year representatives - 75 students;
- 2nd year representatives - 75 students (Table 1).

Table 1. Demographic characteristics

Demographics	Categories	Frequency (n)	Percent (%)
Gender	Female	121	80,7%
	Male	29	19,3%
Age	18-19	78	52%
	20-21	72	48%
Year of study	Year 1	75	50%
	Year 2	75	50%

The questionnaire consists of six components, which in the compilation reflect the overall level of self-organisation of activities.

The "Planning" scale determines the level of involvement of a person in the tactical planning of his daily activities, based on specific principles.

The "Purposefulness" scale measures the ability of an individual to focus on achieving a goal.

The "Persistence" scale measures an individual's willingness to make intentional efforts to complete a task initiated and optimise his actions.

The "Fixation" scale evaluates the individual's tendency to focus on a predefined framework for organising and scheduling events.

The "Self-organisation" scale calculates the individual's tendency to adopt external methods to structure their actions.

The "Present Orientation" scale evaluates the focus on the current timeframe.

Analysing of Data

The summary of the results of the survey was shown in Table 2. After the survey of first and second-year students, a T-test: two-sample was conducted assuming the equal variation was used to test the null hypothesis that students of pedagogical universities are able to develop a self-organisational culture by doing educational and professional activities.

Table 2. T-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

	Group 1	Group 2
Mean	112,1733333	111,28
Variance	291,4425225	338,3935135
Observations	75	75
Pooled Variance	314,918018	
Hypothesised Mean Difference	0	
df	148	
t Stat	0,3082694009	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0,3791554118	
t Critical one-tail	1,655214446	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0,7583108237	
t Critical two-tail	1,976122461	

According to the data presented in Table 2, the means of Group 1 (the 1st course students) and Group 2 (the 2nd course students) are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$ (Table 2).

The average score on the questionnaire was 112 points for 1st year students and 111 points for 2nd year students. However, comparing the empirical and critical values of the criterion, we obtain $|t| < t_{crit}$: $0.75 < 1.97$. Null hypothesis should not be refuted, because it suggests that the differences in the test results of the two student groups can be attributed to the impact of the teaching environment.

4. Findings/Results

The research specifies the following basic concepts of the study:

self-organizational culture is an ordered conscious activity of a personality aimed at goal setting, planning, rational organization of time, as well as self-control, self-analysis and self-correction of actions and behavior during learning activities and beyond;

student's self-organization culture is a personality formation, manifested in the ability of a student to self-organize, to rationally organize learning and cognitive activity of a student. The student's self-organizational culture includes four interrelated and interdependent components: cognitive, reflective, motivational-valuable and activity-oriented, each fulfilling its own functions.

The study specifies that the formation of a culturally self-organized personality of a

pedagogical university student is a specially organized process of interrelated activities of a teacher and students, aimed at creating pedagogical conditions for providing students with pedagogical assistance, support and assistance in developing their experience of behavior based on the culture of self-organization by introducing it to independent formulation and reflection of learning goals in higher education.

5. Discussion

Due to the rapidly changing professional environment, university graduates must be able to quickly respond to society's demands on the level of their training. In the context of rapidly changing requirements for professional training, the need for the development of individual skills and abilities is constantly increasing. The internal reserves of the individual can be aimed at improving basic professional competencies (the ability to work with information), as well as transforming them directly into auxiliary skills or skills for performing a specific job. Currently, education systems around the world are working to find new models and structures that will meet modern requirements. In recent years, the world has been experiencing rapid growth of a new education paradigm, which will replace the traditional one. Despite the complexity of the entire process, the diversity of modern technologies and the differences between the classical and new paradigms can be reduced to a change in the key principles about man as the formation of personality through education. The fundamental idea of the entire system of modern education is the concept of an interconnected, interacting and interdependent human world.

The fundamental idea of education is creativity and innovation. In the modern world, where changes in the field of not so much scientific and technological progress dominate as the way of life of most people, universities are obliged to transfer previously accumulated knowledge to their students, as well as help them solve problems that they have never encountered before. A person must "learn to learn" so that learning is woven into the fabric of his daily life

Having analyzed the fields of scientific research on the problem of forming a culture of self-organization, we can conclude that this problem is one of the most pressing in the field of social sciences and humanities. In a situation of social reconstruction, which is characterized by a rapid pace of social change and new guidelines for socio-economic development; a general orientation towards democratization and humanization, combined with the realities of postmodernism, which divides young people; active devaluation of the culture of ethical consciousness in society - this problem becomes especially relevant for the system of higher education and pedagogy in general.

6. Conclusion

As a result of the theoretical analysis of the key concept of the study, we came to the following conclusions:

The requirement of the modern rapidly changing professional environment from university graduates to be able to quickly respond has identified the problem of forming self-organizational culture among university students as relevant for the theory of vocational education. Independent substantive study of the culture of self-organization of university students in the theory of vocational education is still a new, little developed direction. The culture of self-organization of university students is based on their theoretical knowledge, practical skills, competencies, as well as specific personal qualities, values, abilities and is determined by the unity of its structural components. For a detailed representation of the culture of self-organization of university students, a model was developed that is based on a level depiction of the components of the self-organizational culture, their functions, distributed by type of educational and extracurricular activities.

For further directions we suggest few potential directions for studying self-organizational culture formation at a university:

Case Studies: Conduct in-depth case studies of university departments or student groups that have demonstrated the development of self-organizational culture. Analyze the factors that contributed to its formation and the impact on the overall dynamics within the unit.

Quantitative Analysis: Use surveys and quantitative methods to study the relationship between specific organizational structures and the emergence of self-organizational cultures within university settings. This can help identify patterns and variables that contribute to such cultural formations.

Comparative Analysis: Compare self-organizational cultures across different university departments or programs to understand how cultural formation varies based on factors such as size, discipline, leadership style, and organizational structure.

Longitudinal Studies: Undertake longitudinal research to observe the evolution of self-organizational cultures within a university department or student organization over an extended period. This can provide insights into the sustainability and adaptability of such cultures.

Interviews and Ethnography: Engage in qualitative research methods such as interviews and ethnographic studies to gain a deep understanding of the lived experiences within self-organizational cultures. This can shed light on the personal and interpersonal dynamics that shape these cultures.

Intervention Studies: Design and implement interventions within university units to promote self-organizational culture formation and observe the effects. This approach can reveal practical strategies for fostering and supporting such cultures within academic institutions. These directions can provide a comprehensive understanding of how self-organizational cultures form within the unique context of a university environment.

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